

Extension of the direct strength method to fabricated I-profiles under compression.

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ABSTRACT

The direct strength method (DSM) was developed to predict the strength of cold-formed steel members susceptible to local, distortional, and global buckling or a combination thereof. The method has also been extended to fabricated and hot-rolled steel sections. However, past investigations have suggested that the general form of the DSM provides overly conservative estimations for the compressive strength of I-profiles when the normalized section dimension $\frac{h_w}{t_w} \frac{2*t_f}{b}$ is greater than 10.94. In this case, the cross-section exhibits substantial post web local buckling reserve leading to yielding in the flanges, with little flange deformation. In this paper, the post-buckling strength capacity of such cross-sections is explored, and a modified form of the direct strength method is proposed which expands the applicability of the method to a greater subset of fabricated I-profiles.

Keywords: direct strength method, fabricated, I-profile, hybrid, local buckling

1 INTRODUCTION

Conventional design of hot-rolled sections in bending avoids local buckling entirely. However, pure compression load cases and the adoption of higher strength steels make elements more vulnerable to local buckling (1). Fabricated steel I-profiles – both stainless and carbon steel – with stocky flanges and slender webs tend to exhibit significant post-(web) buckling reserve strength. The direct strength method (DSM) can be a useful tool for predicting the strength of I-profiles, but it currently makes overconservative strength predictions for sections with substantial post local buckling reserve.

In 2010, Seif and Schafer studied the local buckling of hot-rolled sections in pure compression. This study developed expressions to quantify the local buckling limit state in the AISC Specification (2). Seif and Schafer evaluated existing methods to calculate the elastic critical local buckling stress, f_{cr} , which use a fixed coefficient for k , the local plate buckling coefficient, as shown in *Eq. 1* developed by Timoshenko and Gere (1; 3), where E is the modulus of elasticity, μ is Poisson's ratio, and t and b are the thickness and width of the plate, respectively.

$$f_{cr} = k \frac{\pi^2 E}{12(1-\mu^2)} \left(\frac{t}{b}\right)^2 \quad (1)$$

The plate buckling coefficient, k , varies significantly based on loading and section geometry (1). Seif and Schafer used a finite strip analysis to determine the true k value for all sections in the AISC shape database. They develop new predicting equations for the web plate local buckling coefficient, k . The equation for I-profiles under axial compression is given in *Eq. 2*, where h is the height from the centre of top flange to centre of bottom flange, t_w is the thickness of the web, t_f is the thickness of the flange, and b_f is the width of the flange.

$$\frac{1}{k_w} = \frac{1.5}{\left(\left(\frac{h}{t_w}\right)\left(\frac{2t_f}{b_f}\right)\right)^{2.5}} + 0.18 \quad (2)$$

The reliability domain for Eq. 2 for I-profiles is provided in Eq. 3 in terms of the limiting normalized section dimension (LD). For sections where LD is greater than 10.94, the k expressions developed by Seif and Schafer should not be assumed applicable. This is particularly problematic for fabricated sections with slender webs and stocky flanges that exceed the geometrical range of studied hot-rolled catalogue sections.

$$1.80 \leq LD \leq 10.94 \quad \text{with } LD = \left(\frac{h}{t_w}\right)\left(\frac{2t_f}{b_f}\right) \quad (3)$$

In 2013, Rossi and Li further investigated strength predictions for welded I-profiles – including those with $LD > 10.94$ (4). In their research, a validated finite element model was used to analyse H-profile geometries and three steel grades. For sections with $LD < 10.94$, the Seif and Schafer (2010) k equations was used to calculate the critical local buckling load. For sections with $LD > 10.94$, CUFSM – a finite strip analysis software – was used to determine the critical local buckling load. Rossi and Li calculated cross-section slenderness as an input into the DSM equation and calculated a predicted ultimate strength. The DSM predicted strengths were then compared to the FEM results for each section.

This analysis detected a distinct difference in the behaviour of sections on either side of the $LD = 10.94$ threshold. Rossi and Li found that DSM strength predictions are substantially conservative for sections with $LD > 10.94$, regardless of the different methods used for calculating the critical local buckling load.

The purpose of this further research is to identify the section properties that cause this distinct behaviour, and to establish an explanation for why existing DSM forms are inadequate for strength predictions among this category of sections. This research will also investigate the applicability of the DSM to stainless steel and hybrid sections. Finally, a modification of the DSM is proposed which extends its applicability to fabricated sections and sections with $LD > 10.94$.

2 THE DIRECT STRENGTH METHOD

The DSM was introduced by Schafer and Pekoz in 1998 as an alternative to the effective width method in cold-formed steel (CFS) design (5). It was developed to simplify strength prediction, especially for complex shapes with folds and stiffeners. The narrow interest in CFS was chosen for the need to investigate the distortional buckling mode, which is generally unique to CFS members. The core assumption of the DSM is that ultimate strength (P_n) is a direct function of the section's elastic critical buckling loads – local ($P_{cr l}$), distortional ($P_{cr d}$), and global buckling ($P_{cr e}$) – and the yield load (P_y) (6). The DSM equations were codified in AISI 2004, and again included in the updated AISI 2016 (7; 8). The summarized form seen in Eq. 4-8 is from Schafer's 2019 DSM review (9), where the ultimate strength is written purely as a function of the elastic instabilities and yield load.

$$P_n = \min(P_{nG}, P_{nLG}, P_{nD}) \quad (4)$$

$$\lambda_G = \sqrt{\frac{P_y}{P_{cr e}}}, \lambda_{LG} = \sqrt{\frac{P_{nG}}{P_{cr l}}}, \lambda_D = \sqrt{\frac{P_y}{P_{cr d}}} \quad (5)$$

$$\frac{P_{nG}}{P_y} = \begin{cases} 0.658\lambda_G^2 & \text{if } \lambda_G \leq 1.5 \\ 0.877\lambda_G^{-2} & \text{if } \lambda_G > 1.5 \end{cases} \quad (6)$$

$$\frac{P_{nLG}}{P_{nG}} = \begin{cases} 1.0 & \text{if } \lambda_{LG} \leq 0.776 \\ (1 - 0.15\lambda_{LG}^{-0.8})\lambda_{LG}^{-0.8} & \text{if } \lambda_{LG} > 0.776 \end{cases} \quad (7)$$

$$\frac{P_{nD}}{P_{nG}} = \begin{cases} 1.0 & \text{if } \lambda_D \leq 0.561 \\ (1 - 0.25\lambda_D^{-1.2})\lambda_D^{-1.2} & \text{if } \lambda_D > 0.561 \end{cases} \quad (8)$$

In Eq. 4-8, λ_G , λ_{LG} , and λ_D are the global local or distortional buckling slenderness, P_y is the yield load. $P_{cr e}$, $P_{cr l}$, and $P_{cr d}$ are the capacity under elastic critical global buckling, elastic critical local buckling, and distortional buckling. P_{nG} , P_{nLG} , and P_{nD} are the global buckling capacity, combined local-global buckling capacity, and the distortional buckling capacity.

3 MODIFIED DSM AND EXTENDED APPLICABILITY

Post-buckling reserve strength and the interaction of buckling modes were both considered in the development of the DSM. However, the 2006 DSM Design Guide acknowledges that the DSM will predict a low strength for the entire member in sections that have a very slender wall that initiates buckling (10). The design guide goes further to encourage the development of modified DSM strength equations when extending the method to unique cross-sections. Development of modified DSM equations for expanded applicability has been taken up in multiple published examples (11; 12; 13).

3.1 Hot-rolled and welded sections

In 2007, Kwon, Kim and Hancock concluded that “the Direct Strength Method can properly predict the ultimate strength of welded section columns when local buckling and flexural buckling occur simultaneously or nearly simultaneously” (12). Their research made direct comparisons between experimental results and the design strengths in accordance with the NAS, EC3, AISC, and DSM. They also considered modification of coefficients in the DSM equations to better represent the behaviour of welded plates, rather than cold-formed ones. It was ultimately concluded that the DSM was sufficient for design of welded sections. However, none of the experimental test sections in this research exhibited the type of strong flange/weak web dichotomy that this research suspects will be problematic for the DSM.

Kwon continued this extension of the DSM applicability with compression and flexure testing in 2014 (13). Both the 2007 and 2014 paper recommend the modified DSM in *Eq. 9-10* to account for the differences between cold-formed and welded steel sections (12; 13):

$$\frac{P_{nl}}{P_{ne}} = \begin{cases} 1.0 & \text{if } \lambda_l \leq 0.815 \\ (1 - 0.15\lambda_l^{-1})\lambda_l^{-1} & \text{if } \lambda_l > 0.815 \end{cases} \quad (9)$$

where $\lambda_l = \sqrt{\frac{P_{ne}}{P_{crit}}}$, is the local buckling slenderness. (10)

P_{nl} is the capacity under local buckling, and P_{ne} is the capacity under global buckling. This modification accounts for differences in welded sections – relative to CFS – including less significant interaction between local and overall buckling, a smaller post local buckling reserve, and greater residual stress. The change to strength predictions that result is relatively small. For fabricated sections with strong flanges and a slender web, however, the post-local-buckling strength is expected to be much larger than what any of the codified methods currently account for.

3.2 Welded H-profile cross sections

In Rossi and Li’s 2013 paper, DSM predictions performed very well for sections with $LD < 10.94$ despite not being used for CFS as intended. The average ratio of DSM prediction to simulated strength was 1.05 with the coefficient of variation as 0.06. For sections with $LD > 10.94$, however, the same ratio had an average of 0.75 with a CoV of 0.16 (4). The distinction based on limiting dimension is demonstrated in *Fig 1*.

Rossi and Li observed that sections with $LD > 10.94$ exhibited local buckling of the web and very minimal deflection of the flanges. From this, they posited that the flange was developing (or approaching) fully plastic capacity before failure, while the web developed only its local buckling capacity. From this theory, *Eq. 11* was proposed as a simple method to predict the ultimate strength of sections with $LD > 10.94$ (4), where the elastic critical local buckling stress, $f_{cr,w}$, is calculated with the *Eq. 1* from Timoshenko and Gere (3).

$$N_u = 2b_f t_f f_{y,f} + h_w t_w f_{cr,w} \quad (11)$$

The proposed equation performs well – it is very nearly as successful predicting the strength of sections with $LD > 10.94$ as the DSM is for sections < 10.94 (4). While the initial development of this predictive equation appears promising, Rossi and Li’s equation was only evaluated against the dataset of FEM results used to develop it. The FE model used was validated against experiments from the Semi Comp, 2007, project (14). Further interrogation is necessary to evaluate Rossi and Li’s theory. This research will investigate whether it is proper to classify section behaviour based on the limiting dimension and evaluate the theoretical explanations for “strong flange” section behaviour.

4 DSM EXTENSION FOR FABRICATED STRONG FLANGE SECTIONS

A successful extension of the DSM must both identify I-profile sections whose behaviour will deviate from DSM predicted behaviour and predict this separate behaviour. Before pursuing these objectives, it is necessary to have a holistic understanding of existing experimental and numerical analyses for I-profile sections in pure compression. To further interrogate Rossi and Li’s finding of significantly conservative DSM predictions for a distinct subset of sections, experimental results for 116 I-profile compressions tests across 15 separate studies were analysed. The collected experimental body includes fabricated homogeneous sections, hybrid sections (employing different grades or types of steel in the web and flange), carbon steel, high-strength steel, and stainless steel. The experimental results from literature are overlaid with the finite element results from Rossi and Li in *Fig. 1*.

Table 1. Sources of literature for Fig. 1.

Carbon Steel (CS), High-strength Steel (HSS), Stainless Steel (SS), different grade in web and flange (Hybrid)

Author, Year	Citation	Description	Author, Year	Citation	Description
Rossi & Li, 2013	(4)	CS	Kim, 2014	(15)	HSS
Chen, 2023	(16)	Hybrid, HSS	Rasmussen, 1992	(17)	HSS
Salem, 2005	(18)	CS	Zhou, 2013	(19)	HSS
Davids, 1989	(20)	CS	Shi, 2020	(21)	HSS/CS
Jiang, 2023	(22)	SS	Yuan, 2015	(23)	SS
Su, 2021	(24)	HSS	Kwon, 2007	(12)	CS
Shi, 2016	(25)	HSS	Ran, 2022	(26)	SS
Shi, 2014	(27)	HSS	Gardner, 2016	(28)	SS

While a wide range of global slenderness values were analysed, only five of the 116 sections from literature have $LD > 10.94$. Some experiments such as the research from Chen, 2023, demonstrate the behaviour pointed out by Rossi and Li (16). The “proposed sections” in *Fig. 1* are finite element results – discussed later in Section 4.3 – for seventeen new sections designed to expand the evidence of this behaviour. Growing interest in fabricated hybrid sections, as seen in Chen’s work, makes the type of strong flange I-profiles researched in this paper more feasible.

Fig 1. Collected experimental compression tests with Rossi & Li’s FEM results and the DSM strength prediction curve.

4.1 Theoretical explanations

Rossi and Li’s work – covered in Section 3.2 – proposed to estimate the strength of I-profiles with high LD as the sum of the critical buckling strength in the web and the fully plastic strength in the

flange (Eq. 11). Further investigation is necessary, however, to describe this distinct section behaviour and more accurately represent it in analytic equations.

4.1.a Web Ultimate Strength Behaviour

Sections with $LD > 10.94$ tend to have slender webs. Thus, these plates are vulnerable to local buckling. There are multiple methods to determine the elastic critical local buckling stress in the web. Eq. 1 expresses the elastic critical local buckling stress with the local plate buckling coefficient, k , taken as 4.0. This equation can be improved by instead calculating k from Eq. 2 provided by Seif and Schafer (1). The cross-section's elastic critical local buckling stress can also be determined using CUFSM, as was done in Rossi and Li for $LD > 10.94$. While CUFSM is generally a better predictor than equations for the web elastic critical local buckling stress in all cases, it is particularly necessary for sections where the flange is substantially stronger than the web.

The primary reason that CUFSM performs better is because it more accurately represents the end conditions of the web plate. In Eq. 1, the coefficient $k = 4$ is theoretically derived for a simply supported compressed inner element (3), which is appropriate when the flange provides some restraint to the ends of the web, but also rotates and translates with the web under the forces of loading. The theoretical representation of a fixed-fixed boundary condition is approximately $k = 7$. Seif and Schafer's equation for k improves on this theory by identifying that high slenderness in the web plate and low slenderness in the flange will increase k . This describes more restraint provided by the end conditions and increases the elastic critical local buckling stress.

To demonstrate this, Table 2 shows a sample section analysed through five methods. Eq. 1 was applied both with k as a constant and calculated through the Seif & Schafer equation (Eq. 2). Then the web was isolated in CUFSM with pin-pin and fixed-fixed end conditions. Finally, the flanges were included in CUFSM to see how its *de facto* end restraints effected the web buckling stress. In the sample section, the flange is significantly stronger than the web and $LD = 24.42$. As seen in the results, the flange nearly acts as a fixed end constraint on the web. The example section also demonstrates that Seif and Schafer's equation is not always adequate for representing the effect the flange has on web buckling.

Table 2. Web critical elastic local buckling stress calculated through five methods.

	Eq. 1 $k = 4$	Eq. 1 – k from Seif & Schafer	CUFSM Web (pin-pin)	CUFSM Web (fix-fix)	CUFSM w/ flange
f_{cr} [MPa]	80.4	111.3	79.58	140.72	139.16

While CUFSM is very useful for accurate modelling of web buckling, it does have multiple limitations. First, the analysis effort for inspecting a section in CUFSM – while much less than a full FE analysis – is much greater than descriptive equations like the ones developed by Seif and Schafer. Second, CUFSM and Seif & Schafer's equations are not applicable for inspecting hybrid sections.

4.1.b Flange Ultimate Strength Behaviour

Most or all sections that exceed the DSM predicted strength have flanges that develop capacity significantly greater than the buckling capacity of their web. Rossi and Li theorized that the strength in the flanges could be approximated as the full yield capacity. This theory was based on the observation from FE models that the strong flanges in these sections were exhibiting relatively little deflection. However, it remains difficult to determine precisely what capacity can be developed in the flanges before failure. On one hand, it is possible that the flanges are very resistant to deflection and develop capacity beyond the yield strength. There is evidence in the experimental literature of sections with low slenderness exhibiting ultimate strengths greater than the fully plastic strength of the section – likely a result of hardening. The same phenomenon is possible in the flange even after the web locally buckles. When stainless steel sections are considered, there is even greater potential for this type of behaviours because of non-linear stress-strain behaviour with a wider strain hardening domain. On the other hand, it is possible that interaction effects from web buckling will reduce the flange capacity lower than the yield strength. It appears obvious that sections with more substantial flanges will be more resistant to this effect. It is not clear what effect a more substantial web – but

one that still locally buckles – would have on flange capacity. Because we are currently unable to quantify all aspects of this behaviour, we expect that some portion of the observed deviation from our predictions will be due to this uncertainty in the capacity of the flange.

4.2 Classification of Section Behaviour

Rossi and Li's proposal for predicting ultimate strength was to classify sections by their limiting dimension, then apply the corresponding strength prediction equation. However, there is no conclusive evidence that limiting dimension is the best parameter for making this classification. This section discusses the shortcomings of the limiting dimension and proposes alternatives.

The limiting dimension does not account for material strength because it was developed for hot-rolled sections that are homogeneous across the cross-section. It is essentially a parameter for multiplying web slenderness by the inverse of flange slenderness. The sections with the largest limiting dimensions tend to be Class 1 in the flange and Class 4 in the web.

However, if this is in fact the behaviour being approximated by the limiting dimension, then it has multiple shortcomings. First, the yield strength in both the web and the flange must be incorporated to account for their separate effects on plate slenderness. Second, while the equations for determining slenderness classes take the same form in the web and flange, the slenderness classes are not separated by the same class limits (29; 30). This level of specificity is unlikely to make a transformative change on the categorization of sections but may improve precision.

The slenderness ratio (*SIR*) given in *Eq. 12* was developed to incorporate the different material strengths in hybrid sections, with $f_{y,w}$ and $f_{y,f}$ as the yield stresses in the web and flanges, respectively, in MPa.

$$SIR = \left(\frac{h_w}{t_w} * \sqrt{\frac{235}{f_{y,w}}} \right) / \left(\frac{(b_f - t_w)/2}{t_f} * \sqrt{\frac{235}{f_{y,f}}} \right) \quad (12)$$

Both *LD* and *SIR* produce similar performance when plotted against the ratio of predicted-to-observed strength. This is expected because the two produce almost identical results for non-hybrid sections, which is most of the available literature. The slenderness ratio will be used in the remainder of this work because of its extended applicability to hybrid sections.

For sections with very substantial flanges, it may not make sense for our categorization parameter to compare vulnerability to local buckling in the web and flange, as the limiting dimension and slenderness ratio do. Rossi and Li's equation for the ultimate strength of sections with $LD > 10.94$ assumed that the web would locally buckle, and the flange would develop fully plastic capacity. The strength ratio (*StR*), given in *Eq. 13*, was developed from this theory of the strength available in each plate. In *Eq. 13*, the critical elastic local buckling stress of the web, $f_{cr,w}$, can once again be calculated in multiple ways as previously discussed in Section 4.1.a. Determining $f_{cr,w}$ with CUFSM is most desirable. If an equation is to be used, then *Eq. 1* should be employed with k found from Seif & Schafer's method given in *Eq. 2*.

$$StR = \frac{2 * t_f * b_f * f_{y,f}}{t_w * h_w * f_{cr,w}} \quad (13)$$

The two parameters –slenderness ratio and strength ratio – together (shown in *Fig. 2*) capture an approach to understanding and predicting the strength of fabricated sections with strong flanges.

Fig 2. DSM predicted-to-observed strengths plotted as a function of a) slenderness ratio and b) strength ratio.

In Fig. 2(a), there is a clear change in section behaviour when the slenderness ratio exceeds 11.17 (this will subsequently be referred to as the critical threshold). Sections with SIR above the critical threshold tend to exceed DSM strength predictions by 20-60%. But once the critical threshold is exceeded, higher values for the slenderness ratio are not correlated with greater deviation from DSM predictions. It appears that the slenderness ratio is successful in identifying a critical threshold to classify section behaviour but is not well suited to make precise modifications for predicted strengths because of this weak correlation. Further investigation is needed to assess what behaviour is expected in sections near above critical threshold of the slenderness ratio.

4.3 Finite Element Modelling

To fill in gaps in existing research on section behaviour above the critical threshold, a FE analysis of seventeen fabricated sections was completed using Abaqus Standard (31). The model simulates a stub column in compression between two plates. Seventeen new sections are designed to cover a range of values for limiting dimension, slenderness ratio, strength ratio, and slenderness while changing only one dimensions or material property at a time. The next step of this work is to fabricate and test these sections in the lab to validate the model. However, it does make reasonable and helpful estimations of section properties to simulate the response to loading.

To model the stub columns, 4-node shell elements (S4R) were employed. The boundary conditions in the stub column compression test are set with all degrees of freedom (DOF) locked on the bottom plate. All DOFs are also locked on the top plate except for motion along the loading axis (free z -axis translation). Contact properties and friction are defined between the two plates and the column. Within the column itself, most section elements are stainless steel and modelled with Ramberg-Osgood's material model. Using this model, distinct stress-strain curves were found for the four stainless steel grades in the proposed sections. Where carbon steel elements (S355) were used, they are modelled as elastic-perfectly plastic. The shape of geometric imperfections in the stub column are taken from the first eigenmode of linear perturbation buckling analysis, scaled up to the width of the element divided by 200. Finally, the weld in these fabricated sections was modelled with an additional shell element acting as a brace at the intersection of the web and flange.

4.4 Updated Strength Prediction

For sections with slenderness ratio above the critical threshold, it is likely that the section strength is a function of the web local buckling capacity and some greater capacity in the flange. This is the basis for Rossi and Li's method in Eq. 11 and the strength ratio in Eq. 13. The ratio of web local buckling strength to flange fully plastic strength is substantially correlated with deviation from DSM prediction. This is seen in the FEM results from Rossi and Li which form a linear trend when plotted against the strength ratio (see Fig 2(b)). It is therefore hypothesized that a new prediction for section strength can be expressed as a function of the existing DSM prediction, strength ratio, and an empirically derived coefficient to represent their relationship.

The FE results of the seventeen proposed sections in Fig. 2(b) suggest a different trendline. In this analysis, the results from Rossi and Li (2013) are chosen as more reliable because they are based on

a validated model. This decision may be updated in the future, however, once the proposed sections have been fabricated and tested.

The linear trendline in *Fig. 2(b)* quantifies the relationship between the strength ratio and deviation from the current codified DSM prediction. Its intercept is forced through $y = 1.0$. Using the coefficients from the trendline, new DSM equations are established in *Eq. 14*. Notations are consistent with the form used in Schafer’s 2019 DSM review (9), again including λ_{LG} .

$$\frac{P_{nLG}}{P_{nG}} = \begin{cases} \text{if } \lambda_{LG} \leq 0.776 \{ 1 \\ \text{if } \lambda_{LG} > 0.776 \left\{ \begin{aligned} (1 - 0.15\lambda_{LG}^{-0.8})\lambda_{LG}^{-0.8} & \text{if } SIR \leq 11.17 \\ \left(\frac{1}{1-0.0208*StR}\right)(1 - 0.15\lambda_{LG}^{-0.8})\lambda_{LG}^{-0.8} & \text{if } SIR > 11.17 \end{aligned} \right. \end{cases} \quad (14)$$

An initial assessment of performance for the modified DSM equation is provided in *Fig 3*. Performance of the existing codified DSM equations is shown in *Fig. 3(a)*. There is a systematic difference between the observed ultimate strength and the DSM prediction for points with $SIR > 11.17$. When the modified DSM equation – given in *Eq. 14* – is used in plot (b), this systemic difference appears to be successfully accounted for.

Fig 3. Comparison of prediction results for a) DSM as codified and b) modified DSM.

The modified DSM equation gives slightly conservative predictions for the strength of the seventeen proposed sections and very accurate predictions for Rossi & Li’s FEM results. While this is not ideal, those proposed sections have not yet been validated or experimentally tested. Thus, judgement on this issue is partially reserved. The scatter of experimental points is unchanged between the two plots because sections with $SIR < 11.17$ are not affected by the modified DSM equation.

In the existing DSM, the average ratio of predicted-to-observed strength for sections with $SIR > 11.17$ is 0.72 with standard deviation 0.06. The modified DSM equation improves this performance to an average of 0.96 and standard deviation of 0.09. Additionally, no notable outliers are generated by the modified DSM equation.

5 CONCLUSIONS

This paper combines a large body of research on I-profiles in compression to develop an extension of the direct strength method that is applicable to fabricated I-profiles – including stainless steel and hybrid sections. It is evident that fabricated I-profile sections can be particularly vulnerable to local buckling in the web before they reach their ultimate strength. The design guide for the direct strength method acknowledges strength predictions are likely to be conservative for this type of section. These over-conservative predictions were identified by Rossi and Li in their 2013 paper.

The distinct properties of sections that affect local buckling behaviour are individually analysed in this paper. It is concluded that a ratio of the flange plate slenderness to the web plate slenderness is useful to identify which sections will exhibit significant post local-buckling strength. This is the basis of the slenderness ratio developed in *Eq. 12*. Further, a ratio of the fully plastic strength in the flange and the local buckling capacity of the web is useful for predicting the extent to which current DSM predictions will be conservative. This is the basis for the strength ratio developed in *Eq. 13*. The strength ratio is then used in an expression with empirically derived coefficients to modify the existing

DSM equation. The resulting new equation (*Eq. 14*) appears to improve prediction accuracy, particularly for sections with slenderness ratios above the critical threshold. This modified DSM equation is applicable to hybrid sections.

Further work will include the fabrication and testing of unique sections across a range of slenderness ratios, strength ratios, and slenderness values. The experimental campaign will include multiple grades of stainless steel, carbon steel, and hybrid sections. The eventual results of this testing will likely refine the coefficients used to define the critical threshold of the slenderness ratio and the coefficients in the strength ratio term which modifies the DSM equation.

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REFERENCES

1. *Local buckling of structural steel shapes*. **Seif, Mina and Schafer, B.W.** 10, s.l. : Journal of Constructional Steel Research, 2010, Vol. 66, pp. 1232-1247.
2. **AISC**. *Specification for structural steel buildings*. Chicago, IL : American Institute of Steel Construction, 2005.
3. **Timoshenko, Stephen P and Gere, James M.** *Theory of Elastic Stability*. s.l. : McGraw-Hill, 1961.
4. **Rossi, Barbara and Li, Yongzhen.** Extension of the DSM to welded H profile cross-sections. *Research and Applications in Structural Engineering, Mechanics and Computation*. 2013, pp. 1291-1296.
5. *Direct Strength Prediction of Cold-formed Steel Members Using Numerical Elastic Buckling Solutions*. **Schafer, Benjamin W and Pekoz, Teoman.** s.l. : CCFSS Proceedings of International Specialty Conference on Cold-Formed Steel Structures, 1998. p. 4.
6. *Review: The Direct Strength Method of cold-formed steel member design*. **Schafer, B.W.** 7-8, s.l. : Journal of Construction Steel Research, 2008, Vol. 64, pp. 766-778.
7. **AISI**. North American Specification. *Appendix 1: Design of Cold-Formed Steel Structural Members Using the Direct Strength Method*. 2004.
8. —. North American Specification for the Design of Cold-Formed Steel Structural Members. s.l. : American Iron and Steel Institute, 2016.
9. *Advances in the Direct Strength Method of cold-formed steel design*. **Schafer, B.W.** s.l. : Thin-Walled Structures, 2019, Vol. 140, pp. 533-541.
10. **Schafer, B.W.** *Direct Strength Method (DSM) Design Guide*. s.l. : American Iron and Steel Institute, 2006.
11. *The direct strength method for stainless steel compression members*. **Becque, Jurgen, Lecce, Maura and Rasmussen, Kim J.R.** 11, 2008, Journal of Constructional Steel Research, Vol. 64, pp. 1231-1238.
12. *Compression tests of welded section columns undergoing buckling interaction*. **Kwon, Young Bong, Kim, Nak Gu and Hancock, G.J.** 12, 2007, Vol. 63, pp. 1590-1602.
13. *The development of the direct strength method for welded steel members with buckling interactions*. **Kwon, Young Bong.** s.l. : Thin-Walled Structures, 2014, Vol. 81, pp. 121-131.
14. **RFCS2007**. *Semi-Comp: Plastic member capacity of semi-compact steel sections-a more economic design*. s.l. : RFCS-Steel RTD, 2007. Final Report.
15. *Strength and residual stress evaluation of stub columns fabricated from 800 MPa high-strength steel*. **Kim, Dae-Hyung, et al.** 2014, Journal of Constructional Steel Research, Vol. 102, pp. 111-120.

16. *Investigations into the local buckling and post-buckling behaviour of fixed-ended hybrid I-section stub columns with slender web.* **Chen, Shuxian, Liu, Jun-zhi and Chan, Tak-Ming.** 2023, Thin-Walled Structures, Vol. 184.
17. *Plate slenderness limits for high strength steel sections.* **Rasmussen, K.J.R and Hancock, G.J.** 1-3, 1992, Journal of Constructional Steel Research, Vol. 23, pp. 73-96.
18. *Post local buckling strength of bi-axially loaded slender I-section columns.* **Salem, A.H., et al.** 7, 2005, Thin-Walled Structures, Vol. 43.
19. *Experimental and numerical investigations of high strength steel welded h-section columns.* **Zhou, Feng, Tong, Lewei and Chen, Yiyi.** 2013, International Journal of Steel Structures.
20. *Compression Tests of Short Welded I-Sections.* **Dauids, Andrew J. and Hancock, Gregory J.** 5, 1986, Journal of Structural Engineering, Vol. 112.
21. *Experimental and numerical investigation on Local–Overall interactive buckling behavior of welded I-Section steel columns.* **Shi, Gang, et al.** 2020, Thin-Walled Structures.
22. *Stainless steel built-up section stub columns: Testing, numerical modelling and design.* **Jiang, Ke and Zhao, Ou.** 2023, Thin-Walled Structures, Vol. 191.
23. *Local–overall interactive buckling behaviour of welded stainless steel I-section columns.* **Yuan, H.X., et al.** 2015, Journal of Constructional Steel Research, Vol. 111, pp. 75-87.
24. *Membrane residual stresses and local buckling of S960 ultra-high strength steel welded I-section stub columns.* **Su, Andi, et al.** s.l. : Thin-Walled Structures, 2021, Vol. 161.
25. *Experimental Investigation on the Local Buckling Behavior of 960 MPa High Strength Steel Welded Section Stub Columns.* **Shi, Gang, Zhou, Wenjing and Lin, Cuocuo.** 3, 2016, Advances in Structural Engineering, Vol. 18.
26. *Experimental and numerical studies of laser-welded slender stainless steel I-section columns.* **Ran, Hongdong, Chen, Zhanpeng and Ma, Yunmei.** 2022, Thin-Walled Structures, Vol. 171.
27. *Local buckling of 460 MPa high strength steel welded section stub columns under axial compression.* **Shi, Gang, et al.** 2014, Journal of Constructional Steel Research, Vol. 100, pp. 60-70.
28. *Laser-welded stainless steel I-sections: Residual stress measurements and column buckling tests.* **Gardner, Leroy, Bu, Yidu and Theofanous, Marios.** November 2016, Engineering Structures, Vol. 127, pp. 536-548.
29. **CEN (Committee of European Normalization).** *Eurocode 3: Design of steel structures, Part 1-1: General rules and rules for buildings (EN 1993-1-1).* Brussels : s.n., 2005.
30. —. *Eurocode 3: Design of steel structures, Part 1-5: Plated structural elements (EN 1993-1-5).* Brussels : s.n., 2005.
31. **Dassault Systemes Simulia Corp.** *ABAQUS/CAE User's Manual.* Providence, RI : s.n., 2022.